

ANALYTICAL MEHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE DETERMINATION OF ACECLOFENAC AND RABEPRAZOLE BY UPLC IN SOLID DOSAGE FORMS

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Abstract

HPLC are reported analytical methods for compounds either individually or in combination with other dosage form. Method validation is the process to confirm that the analytical procedure employed for a specific test is suitable for its intended use. Analytical testing of a pharmaceutical product is necessary to ensure its purity, stability, safety and efficacy. Analytical method validation is an integral part of the quality control system. The analytical method development and validation for the determination of aceclofenac and rabeprazole by UPLC in solid dosage forms and optimizing the chromatographic conditions. The developed method is validated according to ICH guidelines for various parameters specified in ICH guidelines, Q2. Hence, it was felt that, there is a need of new analytical mehod development and validation for the determination of aceclofenac and rabeprazole by UPLC in solid dosage forms. Retention time of Rabeprazole and Aceclofenac were found 3.03 min and 1.84 min respectively. %RSD of the Rabeprazole and Aceclofenac found 0.93 and 1.18 respectively. %Assay were obtained as 99.22% for Rabeprazole and 99.65 % for Aceclofenac . Regression equation of Rabeprazole is $y = 3098.1578x + 45.2000$. Regression equation of Aceclofenac is $y=0.0002x-0.73090$. Retention times were decreased and that run time was decreased, so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

Key words: Aceclofenac, method development, Rabeprazole, UPLC, validation

Introduction

Analytical chemistry has played a major role in the changes facing the pharmaceutical Industry today. Traditionally viewed as a service organization, the analytical department has become a significant parameter in the drug development process. Indeed, the demand for analytical data has become a critical path activity for selection of molecule for full development.^[1] The pharmaceutical analysis plays a major role in assuring, identity, safety, efficacy, purity and quality of drug product the need for pharmaceutical analysis is driven largely by regulatory requirements. Literature review reveals that there is no analytical method reported for the analysis of and. by UPLC in solid dosage form.^[2] Spectrophotometer, and RP-HPLC are reported analytical methods for compounds either individually or in combination with other dosage form. Method validation is the process to confirm that the analytical procedure employed for a specific test is suitable for its intended use.^[3] Analytical testing of a pharmaceutical product is necessary to ensure its purity, stability, safety and efficacy. Analytical method validation is an integral part of the quality control system. The analytical method development and validation for the determination of aceclofenac and rabeprazole by UPLC in solid dosage forms and optimizing the chromatographic conditions. The developed method is validated according to ICH guidelines for various parameters specified in ICH guidelines, Q2.^[4] Hence, it was felt that, there is a need of new analytical method development and validation for the determination of aceclofenac and rabeprazole by UPLC in solid dosage forms. Present work is aimed to develop a new, simple, fast, rapid, accurate, efficient and reproducible analytical method development and validation for the determination of aceclofenac and rabeprazole by UPLC in solid dosage forms. The developed method will be validated according to ICH guidelines.

Materials and methods

Materials: Aceclofenac and Rabeprazole tablet prepared in house, HPLC water, Acetonitrile, Methanol . All the above chemicals and solvents are from Rankem.

Instruments: ^[5]

- Electronics Balance-Denver
- p^H meter -BVK enterprises, India
- Ultrasonicator-BVK enterprises
- UHPLC Agilent 1220 Infinity LC with high speed auto sampler
- **SOFTWARE:** open lab_chem station

Methods: ^[6]**Chromatographic condition:**

1. Column: INERTSIL C18; 4.6mm X 50 mm; 5microns
2. Wave length:283nm
3. Flow rate:1ml/min
4. Injection volume:20 µl
5. Mobile phase: Mixture of Methanol :water :Acetonitrile in the ratio of 600:300:100 .Adjusted PH 6.14 .

Mobile phase: Based up on the solubility of the drugs, Mobile phase was selected, used as diluent.

Preparation of Standard solution: Weigh accurately and transfer about 20 mg of Rabeprazole and 200 mg of Aceclofenac standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with Mobile phase. Dilute 5 ml of Rabeprazole solution & 5 ml of Aceclofenac solution to 50ml with Mobile phase. ^[7]

Preparation of Sample solution: Weigh accurately one tablets average weight of sample into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with Mobile phase. Further dilute 5 ml of this solution to 50ml with Mobile phase.

Validation: ^[8]

System suitability parameters: The system suitability parameters was determined by preparing standard solution of Rabeprazole and Montelukast succinate were injected six times and the parameters like peak tailing, resolution and USP plate count were determined. The % RSD for the area of six standard injections results should not be more than 2%.

Specificity: Checking of the interference in the optimized method. We should not find any interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of these drugs in this method. So this method was said to be specific.

Precision: ^[9]

Preparation of standard solution: Weigh accurately and transfer about 20 mg of Rabeprazole and 200 mg of Aceclofenac standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with Mobile phase. Dilute 5ml of this solution to 50 ml with Mobile phase.

Preparation of sample solution: Weigh accurately one tablets average weight of sample into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with Mobile phase. Further dilute 5 ml of this solution to 50ml with Mobile phase.

Linearity (for Rabeprazole): ^[10]

Preparation of standard stock solution: Weighed accurately and transferred about 20mg of Rabeprazole standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask.

50% Rabeprazole Standard solution: 2.5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50 ml.

75% Rabeprazole Standard solution: 3.8ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50 ml.

100% Rabeprazole Standard solution: 5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50 ml.

125% Rabeprazole Standard solution:6.3ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50ml.

150% Rabeprazole Standard solution:7.5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50ml.

Linearity (for Aceclofenac):

Preparation of standard stock solution: Weighed accurately and transferred about 200 mg of Aceclofenac standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask.

50% Aceclofenac Standard solution: 2.5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50ml.

75% Aceclofenac Standard solution: 3.8ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50ml.

100% Aceclofenac Standard solution: 5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50ml.

125% Aceclofenac Standard solution:6.3ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50ml.

150% Aceclofenac Standard solution:7.5ml standard stock solutions was pipetted out and made up to 50ml.

Accuracy (for Rabeprazole):^[11]

Preparation of Standard stock solution: Weigh accurately and transfer about 20 mg of Rabeprazole and 200 mg of Aceclofenac standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with Mobile phase. Dilute 5ml of this solution to 50 ml with Mobile phase.

For preparation of 80% solution : Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 16 mg of Rabeprazole into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with Mobile phase. Dilute 5ml of this solution to 50 ml with Mobile phase.

For preparation of 100% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 20 mg of Rabeprazole into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with Mobile phase. Dilute 5ml of this solution to 50 ml with Mobile phase.

For preparation of 120% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 24 mg of Rabeprazole into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with Mobile phase. Dilute 5ml of this solution to 50 ml with Mobile phase.

Procedure:

The standard solution, Accuracy -80%, Accuracy -100% and Accuracy -120% solutions were injected. The amount found and amount added for Rabeprazole mean recovery values were calculated and the results were summarized.

Accuracy (for Aceclofenac):

Preparation of Standard stock solution: Weighed accurately and transferred about 200 mg of Aceclofenac standard into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolved and made up to the volume with Mobile phase. Diluted 5 ml of this solution to 50 ml with Mobile phase.

For preparation of 80% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 160 mg of Aceclofenac into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with mobile phase. Diluted 5 ml of this solution to 50 ml with mobile phase.

For preparation of 100% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 200 mg of Aceclofenac into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with Mobile phase. Diluted 5 ml of this solution to 50 ml with Mobile phase.

For preparation of 120% solution: Weigh accurately and transfer powdered sample equivalent to about 240 mg of Aceclofenac into 100 ml volumetric standard flask. Dissolve and makeup to the volume with Mobile phase. Diluted 5 ml of this solution to 50 ml with Mobile phase.

Procedure: ^[12]

The standard solution, Accuracy -80%, Accuracy -100% and Accuracy -120% solutions were injected. The amount found and amount added for Aceclofenac mean recovery values were calculated and the results were summarized.

Acceptance Criteria: The % Recovery for each level should be between 98.0 to 102.0

Robustness: Small deliberate changes in method like Flow rate and Wavelength were made but there were no recognized change in the result and were within range as per ICH Guide lines. Robustness conditions like Flow minus, Flow plus, Wavelength decreasing and Wavelength increasing was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much effected and all the parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limit.

Results and discussion**Method development:**

Method development was done by changing various, mobile phase ratios, buffers etc.

Trial 1:**Chromatographic conditions:**

Mobile phase	: Acetonitrile: methanol (400:500)
Flow rate	:1ml/min
Column	: INERTSIL C18; 4.6mm X 50 mm; 5 μ
Detector wave length	:283nm Injection volume :20 μ L
Run time	:6 min
Diluent	: Mobile phase
Results	:improper peak elution so, further trial is carried out.

Optimized conditions Chromatographic conditions:

Mobile phase	: Methanol: acetonitrile: water (600:300:100)
Flow rate	:1ml/min
Column	:INERTSIL C18; 4.6mm X 50 mm;5 μ
Detector wave length	:283nm Injection volume :20 μ L
Run time	:6 min
Diluent	: Mobile phase
Results	: Retention time and peak shape is good.

Aceclofenac was eluted at 1.84 min and Rabeprazole was eluted at 3.03 min with good resolution. Plate count and tailing factor was very satisfactory, so this method was optimized and to be validated. [13]

System suitability: All the system suitability parameters were within the range and satisfactory as per ICH guidelines. [14]

Table-1: System Suitability parameters

Sample ID	RABEPRAZOLE		ACECLOFENAC	
	RT	AREA	RT	AREA
Injection -01	3.048	550967	1.846	1103845
Injection -02	3.015	551325	1.826	1114215
Injection -03	3.062	551421	1.847	1103984
Injection -04	3.012	550129	1.854	1104785
Injection -05	3.032	550698	1.832	1116984
Average :	3.03	550908	1.84	1108763
SD :	0.02	522.370	0.01	6327.701
% RSD :	0.70	0.09	0.63	0.57

According to ICH guidelines plate count should be more than 2000, tailing factor should be less than 2 and resolution must be more than 2. All the system suitable parameters were passed and were within the limits.

Specificity:

Table-2: Specificity table for Rabeprazole and Aceclofenac

Sample ID	Rabeprazole		Aceclofenac	
	RT	AREA	RT	AREA
BLANK	3.03	No peak observed	1.84	No peak observed
STANDARD	3.03	550908	1.84	1108763
PLACEBO	3.03	No peak observed	1.84	No peak observed

Retention time of Rabeprazole was eluted at 3.03 min and Retention time of Aceclofenac was eluted at 1.84 min. We did not find interfering peaks in blank and placebo at retention times of these drugs in this method. So this method was said to be specific. [15]

Linearity:

Figure-1: Linearity curve

Six linear concentrations of Rabepazole and Aceclofenac were injected in a duplicate manner. Average areas were mentioned above and linearity equations obtained for Rabepazole was $y = 3098.1578x + 45.2000$ and Aceclofenac was $y = 0.0002x - 0.7309$. Correlation coefficient obtained was $R^2 = 0.9998$ for the Rabepazole and $R^2 = 0.9997$ for the Aceclofenac respectively.

Precision:

System Precision:

Table-3: System precision table of Rabepazole

Conc . Level	Sample ID	Sample wt. (mg)	Sample Area	Calculated Assay (in mg)	Calculated Assay (in percentage)
MID DLE LEV EL (100 %)	Sample-01	501.32	551247	19.7835	98.92
	Sample -02	502.54	563284	20.1664	100.83
	Sample -03	497.62	559842	20.2414	101.21
	Sample -04	503.27	556102	19.8804	99.40
	Sample -05	500.49	551698	19.8325	99.16
	Sample -06	501.46	557461	20.0009	100.00
Average :				19.98	99.92
SD.:				0.186	0.93
%RSD:				0.93	0.93
Conc . level	Sample ID	Sample wt. (mg)	Sample Area	Calculated Assay (in mg)	Calculated Assay (in percentage)
MID DLE LEV EL (100 %)	Sample -01	501.32	1103568	197.4545	98.73
	Sample -02	502.54	1130257	201.7388	100.87
	Sample -03	497.62	1118745	201.6583	100.83
	Sample -04	503.27	1106847	197.2738	98.64
	Sample -05	500.49	1123684	201.3871	100.69
	Sample -06	501.46	1102546	197.2165	98.61
Average :				199.455	99.73
SD.:				2.348	1.172
%RSD:				1.18	1.18

From a single volumetric flask of working standard solution six injections were given and the obtained areas were mentioned above. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD was calculated for Rabeprazole and Aceclofenac. % RSD obtained as 0.93% for Rabeprazole and 1.18% for Aceclofenac respectively. As the limit of Precision was less than “2” the system precision was passed in this method.

Intermediate precision

Figure -2: .Intermediate precision

Multiple sampling from a sample stock solution was done and six working sample solutions of same concentrations were prepared, each injection from each working sample solution was given and obtained areas were mentioned in the above table. Average area, standard deviation and % RSD was calculated for Rabeprazole and Aceclofenac. % RSD obtained as 0.21% for Rabeprazole and 0.81% for Aceclofenac respectively. As the limit of Precision was less than “2” the system precision was passed in this method. [16]

Accuracy

Figure -3: .Accuracy

Three levels of Accuracy samples were prepared by standard addition method. Triplicate injections were given for each level of accuracy and mean %Recovery was obtained as 98.75% and 101.00% for Rabeprazole and 98.87 % and 100.66% for Aceclofenac.

Robustness:**Table-4: Robustness data for Rabeprazole and Aceclofenac**

S.No	Condition	%RSD of Rabeprazole Assay	%RSD of Aceclofenac Assay
1	Flow rate (-)	1.08	0.93
2	Flow rate (+)	0.97	0.69
3	Wavelength (-)	0.75	0.82
4	Wavelength (+)	0.92	1.00

Robustness conditions like Flow minus (0.8ml/min), Flow plus (1.2ml/min), Wavelength minus and Wavelength plus was maintained and samples were injected in duplicate manner. System suitability parameters were not much affected and all the parameters were passed. %RSD was within the limit. [17-18]

Parameters	Rabeprazole	Aceclofenac	Limit	
Linearity: Regression equation (Y=mx+c)	y = 3098.15 78x + 45.2000 (R ² =0.9998)	y=0.0002x- 0.73090 (R ² = 0.9997)	R<1	
Assay (% mean assay)	99.22%	99.65 %	98-102%	
Specificity	Specific	Specific	No interference of any peak	
System precision %RSD	0.93	1.18	NMT 2.0%	
Intermediate Precision Day _01	0.21	0.81	NMT 2.0%	
Intermediate precision day -02	0.25	0.75	NMT 2.0%	
Accuracy %	98.75% to 101.00%	98.87% to 100.66%	98-102%	
Rob ustn	FM	1.08	0.93	%RSD NMT 2.0
	FP	0.97	0.69	%RSD NMT

ess				2.0%
	WM	0.75	0.82	%RSD NMT 2.0%
	WP	0.92	1.00	%RSD NMT 2.0%

Conclusion

A simple, Accurate, precise method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of the Rabeprazole and Aceclofenac in solid dosage form. Retention time of Rabeprazole and Aceclofenac were found 3.03 min and 1.84 min respectively. %RSD of the Rabeprazole and Aceclofenac found 0.93 and 1.18 respectively. %Assay were obtained as 99.22% for Rabeprazole and 99.65 % for Aceclofenac . Regression equation of Rabeprazole is $y = 3098.1578x + 45.2000$. Regression equation of Aceclofenac is $y=0.0002x-0.73090$. Retention times were decreased and that run time was decreased, so the method developed was simple and economical that can be adopted in regular Quality control test in Industries.

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